

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center

Milestone 2 Target Enabling Package

LYN (LYN proto-oncogene, Src family tyrosine kinase)

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Alternatives	JTK8
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1. ABSTRACT

The TaRget Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for Alzheimer's Disease (TREAT-AD) centers were established to provide high-quality research tools and technologies to validate and advance the next generation of drug targets for Alzheimer's disease (AD). Data, methods, and experimental resources are

being openly disseminated through the AD Knowledge Portal to accelerate the discovery and characterization of AD-relevant therapeutic targets. These resources are compiled as Target Enabling Packages (TEPs) that provide open access to validated reagents, assays, and chemical tools. Here, the IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center presents a Milestone 2 (M2) TEP that evaluates the experimental feasibility of initiating a drug discovery program targeting Lyn kinase by establishing and assessing initial *in vitro* assays and tool molecules.

Lyn is a Src-family nonreceptor tyrosine kinase that serves as a critical regulator of immune signaling through the phosphorylation of both immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation (ITAM) and inhibitory (ITIM) motifs. Aberrant Lyn activation has been implicated in autoimmune diseases, hematologic malignancies, and neurodegeneration, including AD, where Lyn expression and autophosphorylation are elevated in microglia surrounding amyloid plaques. To enable pharmacological studies of Lyn function in AD models, we pursued a ligand-based optimization strategy starting from imatinib, based on the observation that imatinib inhibits Lyn kinase but lacks the potency and selectivity required for a suitable probe molecule. Given that imatinib acts as a type II kinase inhibitor and the advantages of this binding mode for kinase selectivity, we reasoned that rational modifications could enhance both potency and selectivity within the Src-family of kinases and provide new chemotype chemically distinct from imatinib. Through systematic exploration of medium-length phenoxyethyl and phenyl amide substitutions, we identified a series of potent and selective type II Lyn inhibitors (e.g., TAD-0411662, TAD-0411836, TAD-0411837), some exhibiting single-digit nanomolar K_i values and >500-fold selectivity over Hck, the closest SFK homolog. Kinome-wide profiling confirmed high specificity toward tyrosine kinases with minimal off-target activity, establishing their suitability as *in vitro* pharmacological probes, while also highlighting physicochemical properties that currently limit their use in *in vivo* animal studies that required brain penetration. These newly developed compounds represent best in class Lyn-selective type II inhibitors within the SFKs and provide pharmacological tools and associated data for dissecting Lyn-dependent signaling pathways in AD and other diseases. Future directions for optimizing physicochemical properties for sufficient brain exposure *in vivo* are outlined.

2. BACKGROUND

Lyn kinase, a member of the Src family (SFK) of nonreceptor tyrosine kinases, plays a pivotal role in transducing signals downstream of immune receptors, primarily through the phosphorylation of immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motifs (ITAMs) and immunoreceptor tyrosine-based inhibitory motifs (ITIMs).¹⁻³ Although the ITAM phosphorylating function of Lyn is considered redundant, as other SFK members, such as Fyn and Blk, are capable of compensating for this activity in its absence, the ITIM phosphorylating function of Lyn is unique.^{4,5} This dual functionality enables Lyn to modulate cellular activation thresholds and function as a master regulator of immune and nonimmune signaling, particularly in hematopoietic, nervous system, epithelial, and endocrine cells.⁶ Structurally, Lyn shares the conserved domain architecture characteristic of SFKs, consisting of an N-terminal SH4 domain followed by a unique region, SH3 and SH2 regulatory domains, and a catalytic SH1 domain.³ Several other nonreceptor tyrosine kinase families, including Tec, FAK, Syk, JAK, and Abl, also exhibit modular architectures similar to those of SFKs.⁷ Among these, the Abl family is the most closely related to SFKs from both structural and regulatory perspectives. Like SFKs, Abl kinases maintain tight control over their enzymatic activity through phosphorylation-dependent activation and inhibition, as well as through the formation of closed inactive

conformations mediated by intramolecular SH3 and SH2 domain interactions. As a result, SFKs often appear in the off-target kinase panels of most early Abl inhibitor development campaigns.^{8,9} Dysregulation of Lyn kinase, either through overexpression or constitutive activation, has been implicated in various pathological conditions, including autoimmune diseases, hematological malignancies, solid tumors, and neurodegenerative disorders such as AD.¹⁰⁻¹⁵

The expression of Lyn in microglial increases in response to amyloid beta (A β), a primary pathological hallmark of AD in humans and a phenotype replicated in murine amyloidosis models of AD.¹⁶ Increased Lyn expression has also been found in human and mouse microglia compared to other SFKs.¹⁷ Furthermore, post-mortem AD patient brains have also shown elevated Lyn levels in microglia.¹⁰ Interestingly, the broad-spectrum Src kinase inhibitor PP1 (4-amino-5-(4-methylphenyl)-7-(*t*-butyl)pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimidine),¹⁸ which mainly targets Lyn, was shown to inhibit A β -triggered neurotoxin production and improve neuronal survival.¹⁰ Additionally, independent studies have documented increased Lyn activation in mouse microglia exposed to A β oligomers, akin to the microglia from the post-mortem AD patient brains.^{19,20} In a detailed study by Gwon et al., the role of Lyn in AD was explored, revealing its significant involvement in A β -induced neurotoxicity and tau hyperphosphorylation via Fc γ RIIb2 phosphorylation.²¹ The study observed a rapid increase in Lyn activity upon exposure to oligomeric A β 1-42 in mouse neuronal cells. They also found that Lyn activation was inhibited in Fc γ RIIb2 knockout neurons, suggesting that Fc γ RIIb2-A β 1-42 interactions mediated the activation of Lyn. An analysis of AD patient brain tissue revealed a three-fold increase in Lyn's autophosphorylation in the hippocampus compared to non-AD controls. Further experimentations confirmed the direct phosphorylation of the Fc γ RIIb2 ITIM at Tyr273 by Lyn upon exposure to oligomeric A β 1-42. Interestingly, the knockdown of Lyn expression significantly suppressed A β 1-42-induced cell death in neuroblastoma and hippocampal cell lines, underscoring Lyn's role in countering A β 1-42-induced neurotoxicity. Additionally, phosphorylated Fc γ RIIb2 by Lyn was found to recruit SHIP2 to Fc γ RIIb2, leading to tau-hyperphosphorylation. Lastly, a novel Lyn inhibitor (KICG2576) was shown to lessen A β -Fc γ RIIb2-mediated neuronal cell death and rescue A β -induced memory impairment in mice. Overall, this study establishes the role of Lyn in AD in the context of A β -triggered neurotoxicity and tau hyperphosphorylation, which are the main pathological features of AD.

Despite increasing evidence supporting the role of Lyn kinase in various disease conditions, selective inhibitors targeting of Lyn remains an unmet need. A primary hurdle arises from the high degree of structural homology within the SFKs, which include Fyn, Hck, Lck, Blk, c-Src, Fgr, and Yes.¹ These kinases frequently co-participate in immune receptor signaling cascades, particularly Fyn, Hck, and Lck, making it essential for small-molecule inhibitors targeting Lyn as a therapeutic strategy to be highly selective for Lyn over other SFKs.²²⁻²⁴ This selectivity is critical to attributing pharmacological phenotypic outcomes to the function of Lyn. While some existing SFK inhibitors that target Lyn exhibit broad kinome-wide selectivity, they often lack intra-family specificity and inhibit a broad spectrum of SFKs, limiting their utility as Lyn-selective chemical probes.

One rational strategy to achieve kinase selectivity is to exploit inactive conformational states of the catalytic domain.²⁵ In contrast to type I inhibitors that bind the ATP-competitive active (DFG-in/ α C-in)

conformation, type II inhibitors engage a DFG-out inactive conformation, often with α C-in positioning.²⁶ This mode of binding mainly leverages structural differences in allosteric pockets that are less conserved across kinases, thereby offering enhanced selectivity. In addition, kinases differ in their intrinsic conformational equilibria and their propensity to sample inactive states, providing a unique opportunity to design inhibitors that selectively stabilize these less populated conformations, as recently demonstrated by extensive solution-phase NMR structure elucidation studies.²⁷ While recent work has demonstrated the feasibility of developing type I_{1/2} inhibitors that preferentially bind the DFG-in/ α C-out inactive conformation (second known inactive conformation) to achieve SRC-B subfamily selectivity, which includes Lyn, there are no reports in the literature exploring the type II inhibitor binding mode to develop potent Lyn inhibitors with selectivity within the SFKs.²⁸ Preliminary data from our group and others suggest that certain type II inhibitors, such as imatinib, masitinib and bafetinib, can potently inhibit Lyn kinase with modest selectivity over other SFK members.^{29,30} Given the characteristic biphasic three-step binding mechanism of type II inhibitors^{31,32}, which involves an initial conformational selection followed by physical binding and an induced fit step that involves residues distal to the traditional ATP binding site, we hypothesized that existing type II inhibitors could be rationally modified to improve Src family selectivity while retaining or enhancing Lyn potency.

To this end, as a proof of concept, we conducted a systematic ligand-based optimization of imatinib, a known type II kinase inhibitor, to develop a series of novel type II inhibitors with enhanced Lyn selectivity within the SFKs. This effort led to the identification of several potent derivatives that exhibit significant improvements in intrinsic selectivity across the SFK family, representing some of the most selective chemical probes for Lyn reported to date. Herein, we report the design rationale, synthesis, and biological evaluation of these compounds with the objective of catalyzing and supporting further investigation into Lyn as a target for the treatment of AD.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Inhibitor Design Rationale

Imatinib, also known commercially as “Gleevec” or “Glivec,” the marketed mesylate salt of imatinib, is a potent and selective inhibitor of Abl (Bcr-Abl) and was first reported by Zimmermann et al. in 1997.³³ It became the first FDA-approved kinase inhibitor for treating chronic myelogenous leukemia (CML). The medicinal chemistry effort that led to the development of imatinib began with the identification of lead compound (**1**) from a screening campaign for protein kinase C (PKC) (serine/threonine kinase) inhibitors. Compound **1** features a phenylaminopyrimidine scaffold substituted at the 3'-position with a 3-pyridyl group (**Figure 1**).³⁴ Hit-to-lead optimization of this scaffold led to compound **2**, in which the 3-position of the phenyl ring is substituted with a benzamide moiety, resulting in a dual inhibitor of PKC- α and platelet-derived growth factor receptor (PDGF-R) with low micromolar inhibitory activity.³⁵ Interestingly, introduction of a so called “flag-methyl group” at the 6-position of the bridge phenyl ring of compound **2** completely diminished PKC α inhibitory activity and improved PDGFR inhibitory activity to a submicromolar level ($IC_{50} = 0.1 \mu M$), resulting in the PDGFR-selective inhibitor **3**.

Figure 1. Evolution of the clinically approved kinase inhibitor imatinib from a PKC hit (Compound **1**). Initial SAR studies around **1** led to the identification of the PKC α /PDGF-R dual inhibitor **2**. Introduction of a “flag-methyl” substitution on Compound **2** diminished PKC α activity and enhanced PDGF-R potency, yielding the PDGF-R selective inhibitor **3**. Subsequent SAR efforts explored two major structural classes, ultimately leading to imatinib through incorporation of a solubilizing N-methylpiperazine moiety. (Highlighted IC₅₀ values reflect activity against key kinase targets, demonstrating increasing selectivity for PDGF-R and BCR-Abl, along with nanomolar potency against Lyn kinase and moderate selectivity over Hck).

Subsequently, the optimization of this compound as a potent and selective inhibitor of v-Abl was reported, culminating in the discovery of imatinib.³³ The SAR studies explored 3-pyridyl, 4-pyridyl, and 3-indolyl substitutions at the 3' position of the aminopyrimidine ring, along with various substitutions at the 3' position of the phenyl ring, classifying the resulting molecules into two structural series (classes A and B), in the presence or absence of the “flag-methyl group” at the 6-position of the bridge phenyl ring (**Figure 1**). Within structural class B, compounds bearing a 3'-pyridyl group on the aminopyrimidine ring and various benzamide derivatives at the 3-position of the phenyl ring (as shown in **Figure 1**) exhibited potent v-Abl inhibition with submicromolar IC₅₀ values. Among these, the initial lead compound (compound **3**), which showed submicromolar PDGF-R inhibitory activity, also inhibited v-Abl with an IC₅₀ of 0.4 μ M, functioning as a dual inhibitor of PDGF-R and v-Abl. However, these early compounds suffered from poor aqueous solubility and low oral bioavailability.^{33,34} To address these limitations, a highly polar N-methylpiperazine moiety was introduced at the 4-position of the benzamide ring, connected via a spacer to the phenyl core, resulting in the chemical structure of imatinib. This modification not only improved aqueous solubility and oral bioavailability but also enhanced potency, reducing the v-Abl IC₅₀ from 0.4 μ M to 38 nM and the PDGF-R IC₅₀ from 0.1 μ M to 50 nM, paving the way for the first clinically approved kinase inhibitor. In addition, it displayed weak inhibitory activity against the SFK member c-Src, with an IC₅₀ value of 15.7 μ M. Our in-house screening of imatinib against the SFKs revealed that it potently inhibits Lyn kinase *in vitro*, with a K_i value of 119 nM and a 13-fold selectivity over Hck, the closest relative of Lyn in the SFK phylogenetic tree (**Figure 1**).

allosteric pocket and can influence activation loop dynamics, was restricted to relatively short substitutions. The incorporation of the N-methylpiperazine moiety that gave rise to imatinib with an extended tail region, was primarily a strategy to improve the solubility and oral bioavailability of the original series.³⁴ In contrast, we employed a ligand-based approach that modified the tail group for selectivity. We synthesized a series of derivatives bearing long tail groups with medium-length, a region of chemical space that was not explored in the original imatinib SAR studies, to investigate the impact of these modifications on Lyn inhibitory activity and selectivity within the SFKs.

Figure 3. (A) Overview of tail region structural modifications explored in this study. Initial modifications involved the introduction of a phenoxymethyl group with substitutions at the para (*p*), meta (*m*), and ortho (*o*) positions on the phenyl ring next to the amide carbonyl group to systematically evaluate the effects of these modifications on Lyn inhibitory activity and selectivity within the SFKs. Compounds **4-28** and probing chemical space not previously explored in the original imatinib SAR. Compounds **29-37** incorporate various para substituted phenyl groups in the tail region, revisiting some reported analogs while also introducing new derivatives. Compounds **38-40** featuring ortho-additions (Y = H, F, Cl) to assess its impact on potency and selectivity. **(B)** General synthetic route used for the preparation of compounds **4-40**.

As shown in **Figure 3A**, we used phenoxymethyl groups bearing different substituents at the para (*p*), meta (*m*), and ortho (*o*) positions on the phenyl ring next to the amide carbonyl group to systematically evaluate the effects of these modifications on Lyn inhibitory activity and selectivity within the SFKs. The selection of the phenoxymethyl group as the tail moiety was based on two criteria: **(a)** it positions the terminal phenyl ring two atoms distal to the amide carbonyl, in contrast to the directly attached phenyl ring in the original imatinib SAR, thereby yielding a tail group of intermediate length, while preserving a molecular architecture distinct from the original imatinib scaffold; and **(b)** the commercial availability of a broad range of substituted phenoxyacetic acid derivatives enabled the efficient synthesis of a small, focused compound library via amide coupling with a common amine scaffold, affording final analogs in good to excellent yields (**Figure 3B**).

We also synthesized a small set of derivatives bearing phenyl groups with different substituents at the para position, directly attached to the amide carbonyl group, similar to the original imatinib SAR, to revisit some of the reported chemical space and explore new analogs for evaluating their inhibitory activity against Lyn kinase. Within the original SAR studies, the “flag-methyl group” at the 6-position of the bridge phenyl ring diminished PKC inhibitory activity while increasing PDGF-R inhibitory activity, indicating that these two enzymes are sensitive to this substitution.³³ However, v-Abl inhibitory activity was not affected by the introduction of the “flag-methyl group,” as evidenced by equipotent inhibition of v-Abl by both compounds **2** and **3** (IC₅₀ = 0.4 μM). This prompted us to synthesize compounds lacking the substitution at this position as well as two analogs bearing Cl and F substituents, respectively, to evaluate the impact of substitution

at this position on Lyn inhibitory activity and selectivity. These compounds were synthesized similarly to the phoxymethyl derivatives from commercially available starting materials using an amide coupling reaction, as shown in **Figure 3B**.

3.2 Evaluation of *in vitro* Lyn Inhibitory Activity and Selectivity

Having synthesized novel Lyn kinase inhibitors, we next determined their inhibitory activity and selectivity within the SFKs using the HotSpot kinase assay, a radiometric, filtration-based method widely regarded as the 'gold standard' for detecting kinase activity due to its high sensitivity and reliability. This assay utilizes γ -³²P-ATP as the phosphate donor, enabling the direct measurement of phosphorylated substrate formation.³⁷ All compounds were assayed against full-length Lyn kinase and Hck, with Hck selected as the initial reference kinase to assess intrinsic selectivity within the SFK family. Since Hck is the closest SFK family member to Lyn, according to phylogenetic analysis, we hypothesized that achieving selective

Table 1. Evaluation of Lyn/Hck Inhibition by tail group phoxymethyl-substituted analogs (**4-28**)

<i>p</i> -substitution (R ₂ , R ₃ = H)				
Compound	R ₁	Lyn K _i (nM)	Hck K _i (μM)	Lyn/Hck
4 (TAD-0411476)	F	330 ± 57	29.4 ± 4.4	88
5 (TAD-0411477)	Cl	275 ± 197	75	273
6 (TAD-0411478)	Br	123 ± 21	47.3 ± 9.6	382
7 (TAD-0411659)	I	159 ± 12	8.6 ± 3.9	54
8 (TAD-0411669)	CH ₃	377 ± 43	18.7 ± 5.3	50
9 (TAD-0411670)	CF ₃	115 ± 26	19.9 ± 1.2	174
10 (TAD-0411479)	OCH ₃	305 ± 88	34.5 ± 4.5	111
11 (TAD-0411671)	OCF ₃	149 ± 59	38.6	255
12 (TAD-0422249)	NH ₂	1.7 (μM)	15.0 ± 3.6	9
13 (TAD-0411658)	NO ₂	60 (μM)	<i>inactive</i>	NA
14 (TAD-0411657)	CN	658 ± 105	75	114
<i>m</i> -substitution (R ₁ , R ₃ = H)				
Compound	R ₂	Lyn K _i (nM)	Hck K _i (μM)	Lyn/Hck
15 (TAD-0411664)	F	152 ± 34	4.2 ± 1.0	28
16 (TAD-0411665)	Cl	254 ± 29	14.6 ± 1.4	57
17 (TAD-0411666)	Br	377 ± 40	10.3 ± 3.3	27
18 (TAD-0411668)	CH ₃	456 ± 37	13.5 ± 1.1	30
19 (TAD-0411737)	OCH ₃	6.8 ± 2.5 (μM)	34.9 ± 7.1	5
20 (TAD-0411836)	NO ₂	732 ± 2.5	14.2 ± 4.3	19
<i>o</i> -substitution (R ₁ , R ₂ = H)				
Compound	R ₃	Lyn K _i (nM)	Hck K _i (μM)	Lyn/Hck
21 (TAD-0411661)	F	92.5 ± 2.8	2.5	27
22 (TAD-0411662)	Cl	8.7 ± 3.9	0.57 ± 0.03	65
23 (TAD-0411663)	Br	30.4 ± 9.2	1.0	33
24 (TAD-0411667)	CH ₃	34.6 ± 0.7	1.0	29
25 (TAD-0411832)	OCH ₃	47.6 ± 31.9	3.1 ± 0.3	65
26 (TAD-0411828)	NO ₂	47.7 ± 11.1	6.5 ± 0.7	136
<i>o,p</i> -substitution (R ₂ = H)				
Compound	R ₁ , R ₃	Lyn K _i (nM)	Hck K _i (μM)	Lyn/Hck
27 (TAD-0411834)	Cl, CH ₃	86 ± 23	43 ± 10	500
28 (TAD-0411734)	Cl, Cl	67 ± 8	3.9 ± 0.3	58

IC₅₀ values were determined using the HotSpot kinase assay (10 μM ATP) with full-length protein and converted to K_i values using the Cheng-Prusoff equation³⁸ to facilitate direct comparison (K_m^{ATP} values: Lyn = 15 μM, Hck = 30 μM). Values are reported as the average of at least two independent experiments ± SEM. Inhibitor constants are given in nanomolar (nM) for Lyn and micromolar (μM) for Hck.

inhibition of Lyn over Hck would translate to improved overall selectivity within the SFKs. **Table 1** and **2** summarizes the apparent K_i values calculated from the IC_{50} values, along with the Lyn over Hck selectivity profiles of the compounds.

3.2.1 Effect of Tail Group Phenoxyethyl Substitution on Lyn Inhibitor Activity and Selectivity

The first-generation of inhibitors we synthesized, bearing para-substituted phenoxy methyl tail groups (compounds **4–14**), displayed submicromolar Lyn inhibitory activity, with some compounds showing comparable potency to imatinib, such as compound **6** (Br substitution) and **9** (CF_3 substitution). Strong electron-withdrawing groups (EWGs), both in terms of resonance and inductive effects, such as nitro and nitrile (compounds **13** and **14**), as well as strong electron-donating groups (EDGs) bearing hydrogen bond donors, such as amines (compound **12**) at the para position, tend to negatively impact Lyn inhibitory activity. Interestingly, despite this observation, halogens, along with other EWGs and EDGs lacking hydrogen bond donors, were generally well tolerated at this position regardless of their size, affording compounds **4–11** with good Lyn inhibitory activity in the submicromolar range (< 400 nM) and improved Lyn over Hck selectivity compared to imatinib. Notably, some compounds achieved excellent selectivity of over 300-fold, as observed for **6** (Br substitution). Overall, these findings suggest that substitution at the para position with halogens, EWGs, or EDGs lacking hydrogen bond donors are well tolerated, with minimal steric constraints, and serves as a key driver of selectivity, either by modulating polar interactions within the DFG-out extended binding pocket or by differentially influencing the activation loop conformational change associated with the induced-fit step of the binding mechanism between Lyn and Hck.

Compounds **15–20** represent novel Lyn inhibitors featuring meta-substituted phenoxyethyl tail groups. Similar to the first-generation, the presence of strong EWGs, both by resonance and inductive effects, such as nitro (compound **20**), weakened Lyn inhibitory activity, while halogen substitutions (F, Cl, and Br) provided submicromolar Lyn inhibitory activities comparable to para-substituted analogs, along with moderate improvements in Lyn over Hck selectivity (25- to 60-fold) compared to imatinib. Interestingly, unlike in the case of para-substitution, methoxy-substitution at the meta-position resulted in reduced Lyn inhibitory activity. Overall, although halogen substitutions at the meta-position yielded potent Lyn inhibitors, substitution at the meta-position was not a significant modulator of selectivity, in contrast to the more pronounced selectivity observed with para-substitution.

Inhibitors bearing ortho-substituted phenoxyethyl tail groups were the most successful among all the derivatives, breaking the submicromolar barrier and reaching low nanomolar Lyn inhibitory potency. All compounds, regardless of the substitution size or electronic properties, exhibited improved Lyn inhibitory activity and selectivity, indicating that a wide range of substitutions are well tolerated at this position. In particular, chlorine substitution at the ortho-position (compound **22**) yielded single-digit nanomolar potency, with a K_i value of 8.7 nM and 65-fold selectivity for Lyn over Hck. Although the Lyn over Hck selectivity was not as high as that observed for the para-substituted analogs, it was nonetheless improved and comparable to that of the meta-substituted series.

Our ligand-based approach revealed key SAR governing Lyn inhibitor potency and selectivity. Substitutions at the ortho position primarily enhanced Lyn inhibitory potency, while those at the para position determined selectivity over Hck. Guided by these trends, we designed two compounds featuring ortho,para-disubstitution to integrate both favorable features. We selected chlorine and methyl substitutions at the ortho position, that drives the potency, as they yielded the most potent single-digit nanomolar Lyn inhibitor (chlorine) and the second most potent Lyn inhibitor without halogen substitution (methyl) in the series. For the para-position, which modulates selectivity, we chose chlorine substitution, representing high Lyn over Hck selectivity (273-fold). As shown in **Table 1**, both disubstituted compounds exhibited a modest loss of Lyn inhibitory potency relative to the ortho-substituted parent compounds (compounds **24** and **22**), with K_i values of 86 nM (compound **27**) and 67 nM (compound **28**), respectively. However, for compound **27**, the Lyn over Hck selectivity improved significantly, reaching 500-fold, making it one of the most selective derivatives we have identified. Although compound **28** also displayed better Lyn over Hck selectivity, the magnitude represented a significant decrease (58-fold) compared to its para-substituted parent compound **5** (273-fold).

Table 2. Evaluation of Lyn/Hck inhibition by tail group phenyl-substituted analogs (**29-37**) and Flag-methyl modified analogs (**38-40**).

<i>p</i> -substitution (X = C)				
Compound	R ₄	Lyn K_i (μ M)	Hck K_i (μ M)	Lyn/Hck
29 (TAD-0411728)	F	3.7 \pm 0.9	<i>inactive</i>	NA
30 (TAD-0411729)	Cl	5.4	<i>inactive</i>	NA
31 (TAD-0411730)	Br	13.1 \pm 6.1	<i>inactive</i>	NA
32 (TAD-0411731)	I	0.81 \pm 0.31	16.2 \pm 5.4	20
33 (TAD-0411825)	CF ₃	2.1 \pm 1.1	23.8 \pm 2.4	22
34 (TAD-0411733)	OCF ₃	0.24 \pm 0.05	14.9 \pm 11.9	61
35 (TAD-0411732)	CN	11.2	39.7	3.5
Unsubstituted (R ₄ = H)				
Compound	X	Lyn K_i (μ M)	Hck K_i (μ M)	Lyn/Hck
36 (3) (TAD-0411727)	C	1.2 \pm 0.2	11.6 \pm 1.2	10
37 (TAD-0411829)	N	5.1 \pm 0.6	37.0 \pm 7.9	7
Flag-methyl modification				
Compound	Y	Lyn K_i (μ M)	Hck K_i (μ M)	Lyn/Hck
38 (TAD-0422334)	H	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>	NA
39 (TAD-0422370)	F	6.9	6.8	1
40 (TAD-0422258)	Cl	14.8 \pm 6.0	4.6 \pm 0.6	0.3

IC₅₀ values were determined using the HotSpot kinase assay (10 μ M ATP) with full-length protein and converted to K_i values using the Cheng-Prusoff equation to facilitate direct comparison (K_m^{ATP} values: Lyn = 15 μ M, Hck = 30 μ M). Values are reported as the average of at least two independent experiments \pm SEM. Inhibitor constants are given in micromolar (μ M) for both enzymes.

3.2.3 Effect of Tail Group Phenyl Substitution on Inhibitor Activity and Selectivity

With the successful evaluation of the chemical space of the tail group with intermediate length, we next designed and synthesized a small set of derivatives bearing phenyl groups with different para-substituents, directly attached to the amide carbonyl group to explore new analogs for evaluating their inhibitory activity against Lyn kinase. As shown in **Table 2**, para-substitution on the phenyl ring generally resulted in significantly reduced Lyn kinase inhibitory activity, with K_i values in the micromolar range, except for iodo

and trifluoromethoxy substitutions (compounds **32** and **34**), which showed K_i values of 810 nM and 240 nM, respectively, and slightly improved Lyn over Hck selectivity. Interestingly, compound **36**, bearing an unsubstituted phenyl ring, which was one of the lead compounds from the original imatinib SAR (compound **3** in **Figure 1**), exhibited potent PDGF-R (IC_{50} = 100 nM) and v-Abl (IC_{50} = 400 nM) inhibitory activity. This compound showed weak Lyn kinase inhibition with a K_i of 1.2 μ M and 13-fold selectivity over Hck, similar to imatinib. The corresponding pyridine derivative (compound **27**) also displayed weak Lyn inhibition (K_i = 5.1 μ M) with only 7-fold selectivity, indicating that the shorter tail groups explored in the original imatinib SAR are not capable of improving Lyn inhibitory activity or selectivity compared to our newly designed inhibitors with intermediate-length phoxymethyl tail groups. These results underscore the unique success of our strategy in exploring intermediate-length tail groups, which led to compounds with significantly improved Lyn inhibitory potency and, importantly, enhanced selectivity within the SFK family, as indicated by excellent Lyn over Hck selectivity.

We also evaluated the effect of substitutions at the 6-position of the bridged phenyl ring on Lyn inhibitory activity and selectivity by modifying compound **5**. As shown in **Table 2**, the removal of the substitution completely abolished Lyn inhibitory activity, indicating the critical role of this position in driving potency, in contrast to PDGF-R and v-Abl, where the “flag-methyl group” tends to have minimal impact on inhibitor activity. Substitution of this position with halogens, such as fluorine or chlorine, resulted in weak Lyn inhibitory activity, with K_i values in the micromolar range, further highlighting the unique requirement for the methyl group at this position to achieve potent Lyn inhibition.

3.2.4 Evaluation of the Intrinsic Selectivity of Compounds **22**, **25**, and **27** within the SFKs

Since the primary objective of this study was to investigate a type II inhibitor binding mode strategy to design potent Lyn kinase inhibitors with enhanced selectivity within the SFKs, we next evaluated the inhibitory activity of a selected subset of compounds against a panel of SFKs to determine: **(a)** whether our novel type II Lyn kinase inhibitors exhibit significantly improved selectivity among SFKs, and **(b)** whether the Lyn over Hck selectivity criteria, initially used as a benchmark, translates into broader selectivity across the entire SFKs. To this end, we selected compound **27**, the most selective Lyn inhibitor over Hck (>500 fold), compound **22**, the most potent Lyn inhibitor (K_i = 8.7 nM) with 65 fold Lyn over Hck selectivity, and compound **25**, which showed moderate Lyn inhibitory activity (K_i = 47.6 nM) with selectivity comparable to compound **22**, as a representative subset of inhibitors for evaluating selectivity across the SFKs.

Table 3. Evaluation of the intrinsic selectivity of compounds **22**, **25**, and **27** for Lyn kinase within the SFKs

Compound	Inhibitor Constant K_i							
	Lyn (nM)	Hck (μ M)	Lck (nM)	Blk (μ M)	Fyn (μ M)	Fgr (μ M)	c-Src (μ M)	Yes (μ M)
22	8.7 \pm 0.9	0.57 \pm 0.03	177 \pm 1	2.4 \pm 0.3	0.885 \pm 0.007	1.3 \pm 0.1	7.5 \pm 1.9	2.1 \pm 0.3
25	47.6 \pm 20.8	3.1 \pm 0.3	295 \pm 46	7.3 \pm 0.5	71.9 \pm 0.6	5.2 \pm 0.4	10.8 \pm 1.5	6.9 \pm 0.1
27	86 \pm 19	43 \pm 10	334 \pm 93	14.2 \pm 7.1	26.0 \pm 5.0	30.5 \pm 4.3	>100	>100

IC_{50} values were determined using the HotSpot kinase assay (10 μ M ATP) with full-length protein and converted to K_i values using the Cheng-Prusoff equation to facilitate direct comparison (K_m^{ATP} values: Lyn = 15 μ M, Hck = 30 μ M, Blk = 10 μ M, c-Src = 50 μ M, Fgr = 20 μ M, Fyn = 30 μ M, Lck = 15 μ M, Yes = 50 μ M). Values are reported as the average of at least two independent experiments \pm SEM. Inhibitor constants are given in nanomolar (nM) for Lyn and Hck, and micromolar (μ M) for the remaining kinases.

As shown in **Table 3**, all three compounds exhibited extensive selectivity within the SFKs, favoring Lyn, thereby supporting our hypothesis that the type II inhibitor binding mode can indeed improve the selectivity of Lyn kinase inhibitors within the SFKs. Compound **22**, the most potent Lyn kinase inhibitor in the series ($K_i = 8.7$ nM), displayed 100-fold selectivity over Fyn and over 860-fold selectivity over c-Src, making it one of the most potent and selective inhibitors capable of inhibiting Lyn kinase *in vitro* with minimal off-target activity against Fyn and c-Src, two key SFKs associated with activating cell signaling. Compound **27** exhibited the highest selectivity toward Lyn kinase among the SFKs, with inhibitor constants in the micromolar range for all other family members except Lck. Although not to the same extent, all three inhibitors showed nanomolar-range binding affinities for Lck, which is expected given its higher sequence homology to Lyn kinase.

3.2.5 Off-Target Kinase Inhibition

To further evaluate the selectivity of these compounds beyond the SFKs, compounds **22** and **27** were screened against a panel of 15 kinases representing each major kinase group in the kinome. This panel primarily included tyrosine kinases (TKs) such as Abl1, c-Kit, EGFR, and PDGF-R, with Abl1, c-Kit, and PDGF-R being the main targets of imatinib associated with its therapeutic effects.³⁴ We also included representative kinases from the calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase (CAMK), cyclin-dependent kinase (CMGC), casein kinase 1 (CK1), and STE kinase groups. These included calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase II alpha (CAMK2 α), cyclin-dependent kinase 2 (CDK2/cyclin A), casein kinase 1 alpha 1 (CK1 α 1), and mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 1 (MEKK1). Given that the original imatinib SAR campaign began with lead compounds that inhibited PKC, and the subsequent efforts led to dual inhibitors of PKC α and PDGF-R achieving selectivity over PKC (**Figure 1**), we also included seven protein kinases from the protein kinase A, G, and C (AGC) group in our screening panel.

Table 4. Off-target kinase inhibition by compounds 22 and 27 against representative kinases from various kinase groups

Kinase Group	Kinase	IC ₅₀ (nM)	
		22	27
TK	Abl1	81	294
	c-Kit	0.85 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.02
	c-Kit (D816V)	2710	5030
	c-Kit (N822K)	1650	144
	c-Kit (T670I)	3150	Inactive
	c-Kit (V560G)	42	35
	EGFR	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>
	PDGFR β	29	89
CAMK	CAMK2 α	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>
CMGC	CDK2/cyclin A	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>
CK1	CK1 α 1	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>
STE	MEKK1	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>
AGC	PKA	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>
	PKC α	>10000	<i>inactive</i>
	PKC β 2	44500	<i>inactive</i>
	PKC δ	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>
	PKC ϵ	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>
	PKC η	<i>inactive</i>	<i>inactive</i>
	PKC γ	>10000	<i>inactive</i>

IC₅₀ values were determined using the HotSpot kinase assay (10 μ M ATP) with full-length proteins, performed in singlicate, except for c-Kit, for which the value is reported as the average of two independent experiments \pm SEM

As shown in **Table 4**, compounds **22** and **27** were inactive against representative members of the CAMK, CMGC, CK1, STE, and AGC kinase groups, indicating potentially higher kinome-wide selectivity toward TK group members over other kinase groups. The current analogs are completely inactive against the protein kinase AGC group. As highlighted above and in introduction, imatinib is a potent inhibitor of PDGF-R, with an IC_{50} of 50 nM, in addition to its intended target, v-Abl (IC_{50} = 38 nM). It was also later established that imatinib is a potent inhibitor of the stem cell factor (SCF) receptor c-Kit, a member of the type III receptor tyrosine kinase subfamily, with an IC_{50} similar to that of PDGF-R. Interestingly, both compounds **22** and **27** inhibited c-Kit potently, with subnanomolar activity (IC_{50} = 0.85 nM for **22**) and low nanomolar activity (IC_{50} = 1.06 nM for **27**), indicating an improvement in *in vitro* c-Kit inhibition relative to imatinib. With these observations, we then screened both compounds against four clinically relevant c-Kit mutations, some of which are known to confer resistance to imatinib (D816V, N822K, and T670I).³⁹⁻⁴¹ As shown in **Table 4**, both compounds displayed a significant reduction in inhibitory potency against the imatinib-resistant c-Kit mutations compared to the wild-type. Notably, compound **27** still managed to retain nanomolar potency against the N822K variant, with an IC_{50} of 144 nM, exhibiting a similar inhibitory profile to that of imatinib. In addition, both compounds demonstrated inhibitory activity against the V560G mutation, which occurs outside the kinase domain and leads to the loss of autoinhibition and constitutive activation of c-Kit, with low nanomolar IC_{50} values (42 nM for compound **22** and 89 nM for compound **27**).⁴²

Based on the initial kinome-wide selectivity evaluation results, we next sought to screen compound **22** (TAD-0411622) against a broader kinase panel to determine whether the general kinase-group selectivity observed in the smaller panel would translate to a full kinome dataset. Here, we first screened compound **22** against 366 kinases in a single-dose, duplicate format at 1 μ M inhibitor concentration and 10 μ M ATP to determine the percent inhibition. Next, we determined the IC_{50} values for all kinases that exhibited more than 50% inhibition by compound **22** and calculated the corresponding inhibition constants (K_i) using the Cheng-Prusoff equation. The results are summarized in the kinome tree shown in **Figure 4**, which depicts enzymes with K_i values below 1 μ M. Consistent with the trend observed in the smaller kinase panel, the broader kinome profiling also revealed that the compound is highly selective toward the tyrosine kinase (TK) group relative to other kinase families in the kinome tree. Among the non-receptor tyrosine kinases, ABL1 and ABL2 were identified as off-targets inhibited by compound **22** with potencies comparable to that of Lyn. Within the receptor tyrosine kinase families, PDGFRa/b, c-KIT, FMS, and DDR1/2 were potently inhibited. These non-receptor and receptor tyrosine kinase off-targets overlap with imatinib's off-targets, indicating that the selectivity pattern may be inherited from the scaffold. In addition, four MAP3Ks belonging to the tyrosine kinase-like (TKL) group were inhibited by compound **22** but have not been reported as off-targets of imatinib suggesting a unique selectivity profile.

Based on the K_i values, compound **22** exhibited $S(100$ nM) and $S(1$ μ M) scores of 0.036 and 0.052, corresponding to 13 and 19 kinases, respectively, falling below each affinity threshold. The $S(x)$ selectivity score represents the fraction of kinases with K_i values below a specified concentration x and is calculated as $S(x) = n_x / N$, where n_x is the number of kinases with $K_i < x$ and N is the total number of kinases tested.⁴³ In comparison, imatinib displays an $S(100$ nM) of 0.031 when measured across a 290-kinase panel in the Ambit binding assay,⁴³ indicating that compound **22** maintains a similarly narrow selectivity profile despite the broader assay coverage.

Figure 4. Kinome-wide selectivity profile of compound **22** (TAD-0411622) constructed from K_i values across 366 kinases. Kinases inhibited with $K_i < 1 \mu\text{M}$ are mapped onto the kinome tree, highlighting preferential inhibition of tyrosine kinases (TK group), including LYN, ABL1/2, and class III/XI RTKs. (Lyn (Blue cycle), Lck (Yellow cycle), Hck (green cycle), Fyn (black cycle), rest of the kinases (red cycles))

It should be noted that many kinase inhibitors currently in clinical use are not selective for a single kinase but inhibit multiple targets.⁴⁴ In some cases, such as with imatinib, this can be therapeutically beneficial, as its primary target Abl as well as the off-targets c-Kit and PDGF-R are all oncogenic or involved in driving cellular malignancy.³⁴ Therefore, the combination of potent and selective inhibition of PDGF-R and c-Kit, along with robust Lyn inhibition and excellent intrinsic selectivity within the SFKs, exhibited by the novel compounds described herein, may present a promising therapeutic strategy for cancer, particularly since strong activation of Lyn, driven by c-Kit D816V mutations in neoplastic mast cells, has been shown to

contribute to cancer progression.⁴⁵ In fact, bafetinib, a type II inhibitor derived from imatinib, has been shown to be a potent dual inhibitor of Abl ($IC_{50} = 5.8$ nM) and Lyn ($IC_{50} = 19$ nM), exhibiting selectivity over c-Src ($IC_{50} > 10$ μ M) while potently inhibiting Fyn, and has been used in the treatment of imatinib-resistant leukemia.

3.3 Evaluation of *in vitro* ADME Properties of Selected Compounds

We next sought to evaluate the *in vitro* ADME properties of selected inhibitors that exhibit Lyn inhibitory activity below 100 nM and greater than 50-fold selectivity for Lyn over Hck (compounds **22**, **23**, **24**, **25**, **26** and **27**). As shown in **Table 5**, all the compounds tested displayed moderate kinetic solubility in the range of 11 to 40 μ M, which can be attributed to the lipophilic and planar nature of the tail groups. This limitation also hindered our attempts to obtain sufficient exposure in mouse models of AD that require brain penetration, highlighting the need to improve the physicochemical properties of this series for *in vivo* studies. However, most of the compounds tested (**22**, **24**, **25**, and **26**) exhibited higher Madin-Darby Canine Kidney (MDCK) cell permeability, indicating the possibility of using these compounds in cellular applications. In addition, all the compounds tested exhibited high mouse liver microsomal clearance values, indicating poor metabolic stability, which can be partly attributed to the phenoxyethyl functionality present in the compounds. This moiety is known to undergo O-dealkylation by CYP1A1 and CYP2B1 liver microsomal enzymes⁴⁶ and, this can be eliminated by employing well-established medicinal chemistry strategies, such as substituting the phenoxyethyl hydrogens with fluorine to prevent oxidative metabolism and improve metabolic stability. We also evaluated the mouse plasma protein binding and brain protein binding of compounds **26** and **27**, which exhibited the highest relative metabolic stability among the tested compounds. Both compounds showed high plasma and brain protein binding in mice, with fraction unbound (f_u) values of 0.006 and 0.015 in plasma, and 0.002 and <0.001 in brain, for compounds **26** and **27**, respectively. These elevated levels of plasma and brain protein binding can be partly attributed to the increased lipophilicity of the compounds, highlighting the importance of further SAR optimization to improve these properties.⁴⁷

Table 5. *In vitro* physicochemical properties and metabolic stability of selected compounds

Compound	Mouse Microsome C_{int} (μ Lmin ⁻¹ mg ⁻¹)	MDCK Permeability			Turbidimetric Kinetic Solubility	
		Permeability P_{app} ($\times 10^{-6}$ cms ⁻¹)	Percent Transport	Category	HBSS Buffer (μ M)	pH (7.4) (μ M)
22	1650	27.2	7.7	High	11-20	11-20
23	1250	12.4	3.4	Moderate	11-20	11-20
24	2130	23.9	6.7	High	11-20	11-20
25	>2400	46.9	14.1	High	21-40	21-40
26	341	35.8	10.4	High	21-40	21-40
27	682	7.6	2.0	Moderate	61-80	>100

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we demonstrate that rational, ligand-based design starting with imatinib, a prototypical type II kinase inhibitor, can achieve potent and selective inhibition of Lyn kinase within the SFK family, yielding a chemically distinct set of novel inhibitors with excellent kinome-wide selectivity. Through systematic structural modifications of the tail moiety, particularly by introducing intermediate-length phenoxyethyl

groups, we identified a series of novel analogs that exhibited low nanomolar Lyn inhibitory activity with significantly improved selectivity over closely related family members such as Hck and Fyn. Biochemical characterization against a broader kinome panel consisting of selected members from different kinase groups revealed that the lead compounds maintained high specificity for tyrosine kinases, while also inhibiting PDGF-R and c-Kit, similar to imatinib, as two of the main off-targets. Evaluation of physicochemical and ADME properties highlighted aqueous solubility concerns, along with high metabolic clearance in mouse microsomes, pinpointing issues associated with the phenoxyethyl moiety and its metabolism, factors that require further optimization for *in vivo* probe development. However, the excellent MDCK permeability observed for the lead compounds suggests that they can still be used as *in vitro* chemical probes for dissecting Lyn-specific signaling pathways in cellular models.

5. METHODS

5.1 General Procedures

Unless otherwise noted, all of the reagents used in the synthesis were obtained from commercial sources and used as received. All solvents were purified by passage through a solvent column composed of activated alumina and stored under an argon or nitrogen atmosphere. All of the syntheses were carried out using flame-dried glassware. Normal phase and reverse phase chromatography were performed on a Teledyne-ISCO NextGen 300 instrument using prepacked silica gel or C18-functionalized silica gel columns available from Teledyne-ISCO, or on a Teledyne-ISCO Combiflash using prepacked silica gel columns available from Agela or Welch. ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO- d_6 or CDCl_3 as solvents on a Bruker AVANCE III 500 spectrometer or 400 at 26 °C. Chemical shifts are reported in parts per million (ppm, δ) and referenced to DMSO- d_6 (2.50 ppm for ^1H NMR and 39.52 ppm for ^{13}C NMR) or CDCl_3 (7.26 ppm for ^1H NMR and 77.2 ppm for ^{13}C NMR). Coupling constants (J) are reported in Hz, and spin multiplicities are described as s (singlet), br (broad singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), and m (multiplet). High-resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were measured with an Agilent 6210 LC-TOF (ESI,APCI, APPI) mass spectrometer. Purities of the final compounds were greater than 95%, as determined by reverse-phase HPLC analysis on an Agilent 1260 analytical HPLC system by following method: gradient table C; column Shimadzu Nexcol C18 (5 μm , 50 mm x 3.0 mm); mobile phase A, 1% formic acid in H_2O ; mobile phase B, 1% formic acid in MeCN; flow rate, 0.5 mL/min; detection wavelength, 214 nm; column temperature, 40 °C.

General Procedure A (Amide Coupling): To a stirred solution of commercially available carboxylic acids (1.5 eq) in 6 mL DCM were added CDI, (1.5 eq), and DIPEA (3 eq). The solution was allowed to stir at rt for 1 hour. To the solution was then added 1 eq of the commercially available amine, 4-amino-2-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]toluene. The solution was allowed to stir at rt for 24 hours. The solution was then evaporated *in vacuo* and the resulting residue was purified by flash chromatography (9:1 DCM:MeOH).

5.2 Synthesis and Spectral Data for Compounds 4-40

Compound **4** (TAD-0411476) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(p-fluorophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **4** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.04 (s, 1H), 9.29 – 9.23 (m, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.7, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, J = 8.1, 1.9 Hz, 1H), 7.95 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.50 (ddd, J = 7.9, 4.7, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 7.34 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.22 – 7.12 (m, 3H), 7.06 – 7.00 (m, 2H), 4.68 (s, 2H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 430.25 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$)

Compound **5** (TAD-0411477) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(p-chlorophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **5** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 9.25 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.94 (s, 1H), 8.68 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.50 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.45 (dt, J = 8.1, 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.94 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.48 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.39 – 7.29 (m, 3H), 7.18 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.05 – 7.00 (m, 2H), 4.70 (s, 2H), 2.20 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 446.15 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$).

Compound **6** (TAD-0411478) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(p-bromophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **6** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.07 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, J =

8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.95 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 7.51 – 7.45 (m, 3H), 7.43 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 7.33 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.18 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.02 – 6.95 (m, 2H), 4.71 (s, 2H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 490.30 [M+H]⁺

Compound **7** (TAD-0411659) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(p-iodophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **7** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.06 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.95 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.52 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.67 – 7.60 (m, 2H), 7.48 (dd, J = 8.1, 4.7 Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.33 (dd, J = 8.1, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.19 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 6.90 – 6.83 (m, 2H), 4.71 (s, 2H), 2.22 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 538.20 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **8** (TAD-0411669) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(p-tolyloxy)acetamide

Compound **8** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.01 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.95 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 8.45 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.48 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.34 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.18 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.11 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 6.92 – 6.86 (m, 2H), 4.64 (s, 2H), 2.23 (s, 3H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 426.20 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **9** (TAD-0411670) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}[p-(trifluoromethyl)phenoxy]acetamide

Compound **9** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.13 (s, 1H), 9.26 (dd, J = 2.4, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.68 (dd, J = 4.9, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.69 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.47 (ddd, J = 8.1, 4.8, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 7.33 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.19 (dd, J = 8.7, 2.3 Hz, 3H), 4.83 (s, 2H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 480.35 [M+H]⁺)

Compound **10** (TAD-0411479) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(p-methoxyphenoxy)acetamide

Compound **10** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: (400 MHz, DMSO) δ 9.97 (s, 1H), 9.25 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 8.94 (s, 1H), 8.68 (dd, J = 4.9, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.50 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.45 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.95 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.49 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.7 Hz, 1H), 7.42 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.34 (dd, J = 8.3, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.17 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 6.98 – 6.92 (m, 2H), 6.91 – 6.84 (m, 2H), 4.61 (s, 2H), 2.20 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 442.35 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **11** (TAD-0411671) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(p-trifluoromethoxyphenoxy)acetamide

Compound **11** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.08 (s, 1H), 9.26 (dd, J = 2.4, 0.8 Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.7, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.49 (ddd, J = 8.1, 4.9, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 7.36 – 7.29 (m, 3H), 7.19 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.13 – 7.06 (m, 2H), 4.75 (s, 2H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 496.30 [M+H]⁺)

Compound **15** (TAD-0411664) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(m-fluorophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **15** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 9.27 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, $J = 4.8, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 8.52 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, $J = 8.0, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.49 (dd, $J = 8.0, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 7.39 – 7.29 (m, 2H), 7.19 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 1H), 6.95 – 6.74 (m, 3H), 4.74 (s, 2H), 2.22 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI $^+$): 430.40 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$).

Compound **16** (TAD-0411665) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(m-chlorophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **16** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 9.27 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, $J = 4.8, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 8.52 (d, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 8.47 (dt, $J = 8.0, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.50 (dd, $J = 8.0, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 7.35 (ddd, $J = 8.2, 5.2, 3.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.20 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.12 (t, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.02 (ddd, $J = 17.9, 8.1, 2.2$ Hz, 2H), 4.75 (s, 2H), 2.22 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI $^+$): 446.30 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$).

Compound **17** (TAD-0411666) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(m-bromophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **17** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.95 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, $J = 4.8, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, $J = 8.1, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.48 (dd, $J = 8.1, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.34 (dd, $J = 8.1, 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.30 – 7.22 (m, 2H), 7.22 – 7.15 (m, 2H), 7.06 – 7.00 (m, 1H), 4.74 (s, 2H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI $^+$): 490.35 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$).

Compound **18** (TAD-0411668) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(m-tolyloxy)acetamide

Compound **18** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.01 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 8.95 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.49 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.34 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.18 (dt, J = 7.8, 3.7 Hz, 2H), 6.84 (t, J = 2.0 Hz, 1H), 6.79 (dd, J = 8.4, 2.4 Hz, 2H), 4.66 (s, 2H), 2.28 (s, 3H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 426.20 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **19** TAD-0411737 N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(m-methoxyphenoxy)acetamide

Compound **19** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.03 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 8.52 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, J = 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.49 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 7.35 (dd, J = 8.3, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.21 (td, J = 8.4, 3.9 Hz, 2H), 6.61 – 6.55 (m, 3H), 4.68 (s, 2H), 3.74 (s, 3H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 442.20 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **20** (TAD-0411836) (N-(4-methyl-3-((4-(pyridin-3-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)phenyl)-2-(3-nitrophenoxy)acetamide)

Compound **20** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.14 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.97 (s, 1H), 8.68 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.95 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.89 – 7.82 (m, 2H), 7.62 (t, J = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 7.52 – 7.47 (m, 2H),

7.44 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.34 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.20 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 4.88 (s, 2H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 457.15 [M+H]⁺

Compound **21** (TAD-0411661) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(o-fluorophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **21** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.13 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.52 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 8.47 (dt, J = 8.1, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.95 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.49 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.32 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.29 – 7.22 (m, 1H), 7.19 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.16 – 7.10 (m, 2H), 6.98 (ddd, J = 11.5, 6.4, 3.7 Hz, 1H), 4.81 (s, 2H), 2.22 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 430.25 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **22** (TAD-0411662) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(o-chlorophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **22** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.11 (s, 1H), 9.25 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.95 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.95 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.50 – 7.41 (m, 3H), 7.33 – 7.26 (m, 2H), 7.19 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.09 (dd, J = 8.3, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 6.99 (td, J = 7.6, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 4.83 (s, 2H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 446.25 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **23** (TAD-0411663) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(o-bromophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **23** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, $J = 4.7, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 8.52 (d, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 8.47 (dt, $J = 8.0, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.95 (d, $J = 2.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.62 (dd, $J = 7.9, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.49 (dd, $J = 8.0, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.38 – 7.31 (m, 2H), 7.20 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.11 – 7.05 (m, 1H), 6.93 (td, $J = 7.6, 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 4.83 (s, 2H), 2.22 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 490.20 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$).

Compound **24** (TAD-0411667) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(o-tolyloxy)acetamide

Compound **24** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.01 (s, 1H), 9.25 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.95 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, $J = 4.8, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, $J = 8.1, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.95 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.48 (dd, $J = 8.0, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.32 (dd, $J = 8.2, 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.21 – 7.10 (m, 3H), 6.87 (t, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 4.71 (s, 2H), 2.24 (s, 3H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 426.25 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$).

Compound **25** (TAD-0411832) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(o-methoxyphenoxy)acetamide

Compound **25** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.01 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, $J = 4.8, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, $J = 8.0, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, $J = 2.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.49 (dd, $J = 8.0, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.33 (dd, $J = 8.1, 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.19 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.04 – 6.93 (m, 3H), 6.88 (td, $J = 7.6, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 4.68 (s, 2H), 3.80 (s, 3H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 442.20 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$).

Compound **26** (TAD-0411828) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(o-nitrophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **26** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.04 (s, 1H), 9.25 (dd, $J = 2.3, 0.8$ Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, $J = 4.9, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, $J = 8.1, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.97 – 7.90 (m, 2H), 7.66 (ddd, $J = 8.9, 7.4, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 7.49 (ddd, $J = 8.1, 4.8, 0.9$ Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 7.31 (ddd, $J = 16.3, 8.4, 1.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.20 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.16 (td, $J = 7.7, 7.3, 1.1$ Hz, 1H), 4.95 (s, 2H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI $^+$): 457.55 [M+H] $^+$)

Compound **27** (TAD-0411834) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(4-chloro-2-tolyloxy)acetamide

Compound **27** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.04 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, $J = 4.8, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 8.51 (d, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 8.46 (dt, $J = 8.0, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.93 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.48 (dd, $J = 8.0, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.43 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.31 (dd, $J = 8.2, 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.25 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz, 1H), 7.22 – 7.17 (m, 2H), 6.90 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 1H), 4.74 (s, 2H), 2.23 (s, 3H), 2.21 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI $^+$): 460.15 [M+H] $^+$)

Compound **28** (TAD-0411734) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}(2,4-dichlorophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **28** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (^1H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.12 (s, 1H), 9.26 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 1H), 8.95 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, $J = 4.8, 1.6$ Hz, 1H), 8.52 (d, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1H), 8.47 (dt, $J = 8.1, 2.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.94 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.61 (d, $J = 2.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.49 (dd, $J = 8.0, 4.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.38 (dd, $J = 8.9, 2.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.30 (dd, $J = 8.2, 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.19 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.13 (d, $J =$

9.0 Hz, 1H), 4.87 (s, 2H), 2.22 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 480.20 [M+H]⁺.

Compound **29** (TAD-0411728) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}p-fluorobenzamide

Compound **29** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.23 (s, 1H), 9.29 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 8.98 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.53 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.49 (dt, J = 8.1, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 8.08 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 8.07 – 8.02 (m, 2H), 7.53 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 7.48 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.41 – 7.34 (m, 2H), 7.23 (d, J = 8.2 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 400.20 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **30** (TAD-0411729) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}p-chlorobenzamide

Compound **30** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.28 (s, 1H), 9.29 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 8.99 (s, 1H), 8.70 (d, J = 4.6 Hz, 1H), 8.53 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 8.49 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 8.09 (s, 1H), 8.00 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.62 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.53 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 7.48 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 7.45 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.23 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 416.25 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **31** (TAD-0411730) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}p-bromobenzamide

Compound **31** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.28 (s, 1H), 9.29 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.98 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.53 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.51 – 8.47 (m, 1H), 8.09 (d, J = 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.92 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.76 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.53 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz,

1H), 7.48 (dd, J = 8.3, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.45 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 7.23 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 460.25 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **32** (TAD-0411731) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}p-iodobenzamide

Compound **32** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.26 (s, 1H), 9.29 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.98 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, J = 4.9, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 8.53 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.49 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.1 Hz, 1H), 8.09 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.95 – 7.90 (m, 2H), 7.79 – 7.73 (m, 2H), 7.53 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 7.48 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.2 Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 7.22 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 508.30 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **33** (TAD-0411825) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}p-(trifluoromethyl)benzamide

Compound **33** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.33 (s, 1H), 9.29 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 9.00 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 8.53 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.49 (dt, J = 8.0, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 8.12 – 8.07 (m, 3H), 7.54 (dd, J = 8.2, 4.2 Hz, 3H), 7.51 – 7.43 (m, 2H), 7.23 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 450.25 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **34** (TAD-0411733) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}p-trifluoroanisamide

Compound **34** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.33 (s, 1H), 9.28 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.99 (s, 1H), 8.70 (dd, J = 4.7, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 8.52 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 8.49 (dt, J =

8.1, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 8.13 – 8.04 (m, 3H), 7.53 (dd, J = 8.7, 3.3 Hz, 3H), 7.51 – 7.41 (m, 2H), 7.23 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 466.20 [M+H]⁺.

Compound **35** (TAD-0411732) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}p-cyanobenzamide

Compound **35** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.46 (s, 1H), 9.28 (dd, J = 2.3, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 9.00 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.7, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.52 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 8.48 (dt, J = 8.1, 1.9 Hz, 1H), 8.14 – 8.09 (m, 3H), 8.06 – 8.00 (m, 2H), 7.56 – 7.46 (m, 2H), 7.44 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.24 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 407.30 [M+H]⁺)

Compound **36** (TAD-0411727) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}benzamide

Compound **36** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 500 MHz, DMSO δ 10.22 (s, 1H), 9.28 (dd, J = 2.3, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 8.99 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 8.52 (dd, J = 5.2, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 8.49 (dt, J = 8.1, 1.9 Hz, 1H), 8.09 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 7.98 – 7.94 (m, 2H), 7.62 – 7.57 (m, 1H), 7.56 – 7.53 (m, 2H), 7.53 – 7.48 (m, 2H), 7.44 (dd, J = 5.1, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.22 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 2.23 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 382.20 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **37** (TAD-0411829) N-{3-[4-(3-pyridyl)-2-pyrimidinylamino]-4-tolyl}-2-pyridinecarboxamide

Compound **37** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: (500 MHz, DMSO) δ 10.58 (s, 1H), 9.29 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 9.00 (s, 1H), 8.74 (dt, J = 4.7, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.7, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 8.53 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 8.49 (dt, J = 8.1, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 8.27 (d, J = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 8.16 (dt, J = 7.9, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 8.07 (td, J

= 7.7, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.68 (ddd, J = 7.6, 4.7, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.57 (dd, J = 8.2, 2.3 Hz, 1H), 7.53 (dd, J = 8.0, 4.8 Hz, 1H), 7.44 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.23 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 383.20 [M+H]⁺

Compound **38** (TAD-0422334) 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-N-(3-((4-(pyridin-3-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)phenyl)acetamide

Compound **38** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (1H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.10 (s, 1H), 9.80 (s, 1H), 9.34 (d, J = 1.5 Hz, 1H), 8.71 (d, J = 4.4 Hz, 1H), 8.59 (t, J = 8.9, 5.1 Hz, 2H), 8.27 (s, 1H), 7.52 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 7.49-7.46 (m, J = 5.16 Hz, 2H), 7.36 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 7.27-7.19 (m, 2H), 7.04 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 4.74 (s, 2H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 432.3 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **39** (TAD-0422369) 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-N-(4-fluoro-3-((4-(pyridin-3-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)phenyl)acetamide

Compound **39** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (1H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.17 (s, 1H), 9.27 (d, J = 6.9 Hz, 2H), 8.69 (d, J = 3.6 Hz, 1H), 8.55 (d, J = 4.8 Hz, 1H), 8.49 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 8.19 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 1H), 7.52-7.46 (m, 2H), 7.35 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 3H), 7.24-7.20 (m, 1H), 7.03 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 4.74 (s, 2H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 450.3 [M+H]⁺).

Compound **40** (TAD-0422258) N-(4-chloro-3-((4-(pyridin-3-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl)amino)phenyl)-2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetamide

Compound **40** was synthesized according to general procedure A. (¹H NMR: 400 MHz, DMSO δ 10.28 (s, 1H), 9.28 (d, J = 1.9 Hz, 1H), 8.98 (s, 1H), 8.69 (dd, J = 4.8, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 8.57 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 8.49 (d, J = 8.0, 1H), 8.29 (d, J = 2.1 Hz, 1H), 7.52 (d, J = 5.16 Hz, 1H), 7.48-7.40 (m, 3H), 7.35 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 7.03 (d, J = 9.0 Hz, 2H), 4.74 (s, 2H). LRMS m/z (ESI+): 466.0 [M+H]⁺).

5.3 Hotspot Kinase Assay Protocol

The assay was carried out at Reaction Biology Corporation according to a previously described protocol.⁴⁸ The corresponding substrate was first prepared in a freshly constituted base reaction buffer (20 mM Hepes (pH 7.5), 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM EGTA, 0.01% Brij35, 0.02 mg/ml BSA, 0.1 mM Na₃VO₄, 2 mM DTT, 1% DMSO) and necessary cofactors were introduced to the substrate solution. After that, the kinase was added, ensuring gentle mixing for a homogeneous solution. Using the Echo550 acoustic technology, inhibitors dissolved in 100% DMSO (10 mM) were introduced into the kinase-substrate-cofactor mixture in nanoliter volumes to create a 10-point, three-fold dilution series starting from 100, 10, or 1 μM inhibitor concentrations. This mixture was subsequently incubated at room temperature for 20 minutes to facilitate optimal interactions. The kinase reaction was initiated by adding ³³P-ATP (10 μM) into the mixture. Following this, the reaction was allowed to proceed for 2 hours at room temperature to ensure completion. After the incubation, the kinase activity was detected using the P81 filter-binding method.

5.4 Evaluation of *in vitro* Physicochemical and PK Properties

In vitro physicochemical and PK properties of selected compounds were determined at Q² Solutions using well-established protocols. Assays involving LC-MS/MS analysis were performed using an LC-MS/MS system equipped with an MDS SCIEX API 4000 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer, unless otherwise noted. All reagents used were of HPLC grade, and mobile phases were adjusted using various aqueous and organic solvent mixtures to optimize analyte retention. All LC-MS/MS methods were developed with a lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) of 2.5 nM. The typical calibration curve ranged from 2.5 to 5000 nM. A detailed description of each assay is provided below.

5.4.1 Kinetics Solubility Assay

The assay was conducted to rank-order the test compounds based on their apparent solubility in two aqueous buffer systems: Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) with 25 mM HEPES, and 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). Terfenadine and spironolactone (50 mM in DMSO) were included as internal standards. The assay was conducted in clear, flat-bottom polystyrene 96-well plates, where each well was preloaded with 198 μL of buffer and scanned using a NEPHELOStar Plus nephelometer to obtain background scatter (pre-read). After that, 2 μL of compound stock solution (prepared in DMSO) was added to the wells, achieving a final DMSO concentration that was kept constant across all wells. The compound stock was serially diluted in DMSO to prepare a concentration range, and each dilution was tested individually by dispensing into buffer-containing wells as above. Plates were gently mixed and incubated for 2 hours at room temperature, prior to repetition of the nephelometric measurements using the same scan mode (single scan measurement). Solubility was assessed by comparing final nephelometric signals to the pre-read background, and the solubility cutoff was defined as five times the average background value.

5.4.2 MDCK Permeability Assay

The MDCK cell-based permeability assay was performed to estimate the intestinal absorption potential of test compounds. Dexamethasone (10 mM in DMSO) was included as a control compound. The test compounds were first diluted to 200 μM by mixing 2 μL of the 10 mM stock solution with 98 μL of DMSO (1:50 dilution). MDCK cells were cultured on permeable supports, and prior to dosing, the apical chamber buffer was removed and rinsed three times with HBSS supplemented with HEPES (HBSSH). A final aliquot of 150 μL HBSSH containing cyclosporin A (CSA) was added to the apical chamber. The receiver plate was filled with 300 μL of HBSSH containing CSA, and the apical plate was placed atop the receiver plate and preincubated for 30 minutes at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5% CO_2 . A pre-dose reference plate was prepared by mixing 50 μL of stop reagent (containing internal standard) with 125 μL of HBSSH. A 25 μL aliquot of the test compound solution was taken prior to dosing and added to this pre-dose plate, mixed thoroughly, and submitted for LC-MS/MS analysis. After that, 150 μL of the test compound solution was added to a fresh MilliCell receiver plate, and the post-dose incubation was carried out at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5% CO_2 for 60 minutes, followed by preparation of post-dose samples by adding 50 μL of stop reagent (with internal standard) and 125 μL of HBSSH to a new plate. A 25 μL aliquot from the post-dose solution was transferred to this new plate, mixed well, and submitted for LC-MS/MS analysis. Simultaneously, 150 μL of the test compound solution was added to the apical chamber of the cell plate, and the cells were incubated for 60 minutes at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Following this, an apical sample plate was prepared by adding 50 μL of stop reagent (with internal standard) and 125 μL of HBSSH. A 25 μL aliquot was collected from the apical chamber, added to the sample plate, mixed, and submitted for LC-MS/MS analysis. Fluorescence measurements were performed using a plate reader with excitation at 590 nm and emission at 635 nm.

5.4.3 Mouse Microsomal Intrinsic Clearance

The assay was conducted using pooled mouse liver microsomes (0.25 mg/mL final concentration) to estimate metabolic stability of the test compounds. The microsomal incubation buffer consisted of 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) containing 0.4066 g/L $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, pre-warmed to 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The final protein concentration in the reaction was 0.28 mg/mL. Test compound stock solutions were prepared in DMSO. Internal standard controls included labetalol, imipramine, and diclofenac, each prepared at 10 mM in DMSO (16.42 mg, 15.84 mg, and 15.9 mg in 5 mL DMSO, respectively). Standards were stored sealed at ambient temperature or 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ until use. Microsomal incubations were performed in 96-well plates pre-warmed to 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for approximately 15 minutes. To each well, 222.5 μL of microsomal solution was added, and equilibrated for 10 minutes at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with shaking. The reactions were initiated by adding 2.5 μL of compound stock solution followed by 25 μL of NADPH solution and mixed well. For negative controls, 25 μL of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) was added in place of NADPH. Immediately after NADPH addition, a 20 μL aliquot was withdrawn from the reaction mixture and quenched with 80 μL of metabolic stability stop reagent containing internal standard. After the designated incubation period, a second 20 μL aliquot was withdrawn and similarly quenched. For the negative control plate, samples were collected and quenched after a 45-minute incubation under identical conditions. All quenched samples were centrifuged at ~ 4000 rpm for at least 15 minutes at room temperature. The supernatants were analyzed using LC-MS/MS method.

5.4.4 Mouse Plasma Protein Binding Assay

The assay was conducted to determine the plasma protein binding of the test compounds using equilibrium dialysis. Mouse plasma (30 mL) was thawed on the day of use and adjusted to pH 7.4 ± 0.05 using either 4:1 (v/v) H₂O:25% phosphoric acid or 2:1 (v/v) H₂O:sodium hydroxide. Internal standards included labetalol, imipramine, and diclofenac (10 mM in DMSO). Verapamil (10 mM in DMSO) was included as a control compound. Following dilution of test compounds into DMSO, 2 µL of each dilution was added to 500 µL of blank mouse plasma. A serial dilution was prepared in DMSO across a concentration range of 5 µM to 0.0025 µM, starting from a 250 µM primary dilution. Equilibrium dialysis was conducted using a Teflon block with a dialysis membrane separating the two chambers. To one side of the membrane, 100 µL of 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) was added. To the opposite side, 100 µL of the plasma solution containing the test compound was added. The dialysis block was sealed with a breathable adhesive film to prevent evaporation and incubated for 4.5 hours at 37 °C while shaking at 167 rpm. All samples were prepared and analyzed in triplicate. At the end of the incubation, a 5 µL aliquot was withdrawn from the protein-containing side of the membrane and transferred to a PCR plate. To this, 5 µL of DMSO, 50 µL of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), and 125 µL of quench solution were added and mixed thoroughly. In parallel, a 50 µL aliquot from the buffer side of the membrane was also collected and processed by adding 5 µL of DMSO, 5 µL of blank plasma, and 125 µL of quench solution. All samples were mixed and centrifuged at ~4000 rpm for 30 minutes at room temperature. The resulting supernatants were analyzed by LC-MS/MS.

5.4.5 Mouse Brain Protein Binding Assay

Similar to the plasma protein binding assay, the brain tissue protein binding of test compounds was evaluated using equilibrium dialysis with mouse brain homogenate. Fresh brain tissue was weighed and homogenized in ice using a probe sonicator for 2 minutes (amplitude 10) in two volumes (w:v) of 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). Homogenization duration was adjusted as needed based on tissue mass. Test compound stock solutions were prepared in DMSO. Internal standards included labetalol, imipramine, and diclofenac (10 mM in DMSO), and verapamil (10 mM in DMSO) was included as a control compound. Following dilution into DMSO, 2.8 µL of the test compound was added to 700 µL of blank brain homogenate. Serial dilutions were prepared in DMSO over a concentration range of 5 µM to 0.0025 µM, starting from a 250 µM primary dilution. The remaining steps, including equilibrium dialysis setup, incubation, sample collection, quenching, centrifugation, and LC-MS/MS analysis, were performed as described for the plasma protein binding assay.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

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KEY WORDS

Lyn, Src, Alzheimer's disease, Type II Kinase Inhibitors

DATA AVAILABILITY

Datasets will be made available via the AD Knowledge Portal.

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